

EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON SELF-ESTEEM AMONG WORKING WOMEN

Dr. M. Madan Mohan

Associate Professor, Department of Physical Education, A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on self-esteem among working women. To achieve the purpose of the present study, thirty women from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 25 to 45 years. The subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen each. Group I acted as Experimental Group I (Yogic practices) and Group II acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. The variable to be used in the present study was collected from all subjects before they have to treat with the respective treatments. It was assumed as pre-test. After completion of treatment they were tested again as it was in the pre-test on all variables used in the present study. This test was assumed as post-test. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the treatment effect of the training programmes on all the variables used in the study. It was observed that the six weeks of yogic practices have significantly improved the self-esteem.

Key Words: Yogic Practices, Self-Esteem.

Introduction:

Yogis of the past had not paid very much attention to the body, as they focused all their energy on contemplation and meditation. The new generation of yogis however, developed a system where different exercises in conjunction with deep breathing and meditation, would help keep a body young and prolong life. Yoga is like a blessing for those who love to have fit body. It is extremely beneficial in strength and endurance building. Sages and saints from centuries in India have performed this miraculous art to achieve a stress free temper and disease free body. Yoga through its different asana helps in developing a better coordination between different body organs along with your mind and your soul leaving you feel extremely fit and fine. Apart from providing you with vigor and activeness, yoga is also helpful in healing the diseases persisting in your body thus leaving you with more strength and endurance. In recent times there is a growing awareness among the people about the efficacy and utility of yoga in keeping one fit at physical, mental, emotional, social and spiritual planes. These systems are emerging as the effective methods and means to improve the total personality and to build a healthy society. Above all these systems are adopted as a way of life rather than a mode of treatment.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on self-esteem among working women. To achieve the purpose of the present study, thirty women from A.V.V.M. Sri Pushpam College, Poondi, Thanjavur were selected as subjects at random and their ages ranged from 25 to 45 years. The subjects were divided into two equal groups of fifteen each. Group I acted as Experimental Group I (Yogic practices) and Group II acted as Control Group. The requirement of the experiment procedures, testing as well as exercise schedule was explained to the subjects so as to get full co-operation of the effort required on their part and prior to the administration of the study. The variable to be used in the present study was collected from all subjects before they have to treat with the respective treatments. It was assumed as pre-test. After completion of treatment they were tested again as it was in the pre-test on all variables used in the present study. This test was assumed as post-test. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the treatment effect of the training programmes on all the variables used in the study.

Results:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Self Esteem of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	12.51	12.24	BG	0.558	1	0.558	0.247
			WG	63.304	28	2.261	
Post Test Mean	18.38	12.44	BG	264.457	1	264.457	118.313*
			WG	62.586	28	2.235	
Adjusted	18.33	12.49	BG	254.265	1	254.265	123.242*

Post Mean			WG	55.705	27	2.063	
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* Significant at 0.05 level

Table value for df 1 and 28 was 4.20

Table value for df 1 and 27 was 4.21

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of self esteem of experimental and control groups were 18.33 and 12.49 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 123.24 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference among experimental and control groups on self esteem. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups also differ significantly. The pre and post mean values of self esteem of both control and experimental groups are graphically represented in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram of Self Esteem of Experimental and Control Groups

Conclusion:

It was observed that the six weeks of yogic practices have significantly improved the self-esteem.

References:

1. Amita, S., Prabhakar, S., Manoj, I., Harminder, S., Pavan, T. (2009).Effect of yoga-nidra on blood glucose level in diabetic patients. Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology, Vol.53 (1): PP.97-101.
2. Andreasi, V., Michelin, E., Rinaldi, A, E., Burini, R, C. (2010). Physical fitness and associations with anthropometric measurements in 7 to 15-year-old school children. Journal De Pediatria, Vol.86 (6): PP.497-502.
3. Anne-Marie E Alberse, Annelou LC de Vries, Wieteke S Elzinga Thomas D Steensma (2019). Self-perception of transgender clinic referred gender diverse children and adolescents. Clin Child Psychiatry. 24(2): 388–401.
4. Anurodh, S. S. (2017). Effect of transcendental meditation on balance ability. International Journal of Yoga, Physiotherapy and Physical Education, 2, 1.
5. Astrup (2001). The role of dietary fat in the prevention and treatment of obesity, Efficacy and safety of low-fat diets. International Journal of Obesity Related Metabolism disorder, Vol.25 (1): PP.S46-50.
6. Bera, T, K., Rajapurkar, M, V. (1993). Body composition, cardiovascular endurance and anaerobic power of yogic practitioner. Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology, Vol.37 (3): PP.225-8.
7. Bertisch, S, M., Wee, C, C., McCarthy, E, P. (2008).Use of complementary and alternative therapies by overweight and obese adults. Journal of Research and Education in Complementary and Integrative Medical Therapies, Vol.16 (7): PP.1610-5.
8. Chatterjee, F., Bruce, S, A., Woldege,R,C. (2010)Effect of yogic Exercises on human Growth hormone in a middle aged group: a pilot study. Yoga Mimamsa a Quarterly Journal, vol XLII.1, PP.40-47.
9. Chen, K, M., and Tseng,W,S.(2008).Effect of newly developed silver yoga exercise program for female seniors. Journal of Nursing and Resarch, Vol.6 (1): PP.37-46.
10. Chen, T, L., Mao,H,C., Lai ,C,H., Li ,C,Y., Kuo,C,H.(2009). The effect of yoga exercise intervention on health related physical fitness in school-age asthmatic children. The Journal of Nursing-Taiwan, Vol.56 (2): PP.42-52.

11. Sandhu, G.S. (2002). Psychology in Sports: A Contemporary Approach. New Delhi: Friends Publications, pp.31-33.
12. Silva, J. M. & Weinberg, R. S. (1984). Psychological Foundations of Sports. Illinois: Human Kinetics.
13. Swami Sivanandha (2001). Radiant Health through Yoga. The orient processors, Sivakashi.
14. Yadav, Y.P. & Rachna (1998). Art of Yoga. India: Friends Publications.
15. Suresh, Kumar M. (2017). Influence of Yoga Practices on Blood Pressure among Rural College Girls. Star International Research Journal, 5, 1(3).
16. C. A .Vijayarani, Dr. V. Vallimurugan & M. Suresh Kumar (2012). Influence of Yogic Practices on Selected Physiological and Psychological Variables of Adolescent Boys. Recent Research in Science and Technology. 3,1.
17. Eswaramoorthy, A. & Suresh Kumar, M. (2020). Effect of yogic practices and aerobic training on flexibility among physical education students. Purakala, 31,8, 417-420.
18. Suresh, Kumar M. (2020). Investigation of the Changes on Selected Physical Fitness Parameters in Response to SAQ Training among College Women Students. Alochana Chakra Journal, 9, 4, 5121-5124.